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Research Article

Bioinformatic Analysis of Human TLR4 Coding Variations Associated with Ocular Infection: A Structural Prediction and Molecular Docking Studies

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ABSTRACT

In 2023, Pakistan faced a widespread outbreak of conjunctivitis, affecting nearly 400,000 individuals. The rapid transmission was driven by environmental factors, infectious agents, and allergens, with common symptoms including eye redness, swelling, tearing, and discharge. In response, a pioneering bioinformatics study examined the TLR4 gene variants, given TLR4 role in immune response, although direct genetic links to conjunctivitis are not yet established. Using Swiss Model and SAVESV6.1, a 3D model of TLR4 was developed, verified with a QMEAN-Z score of -0.81 and a ProSA score of -7.51, affirming its reliability. This study identified 82 highly deleterious nsSNPs through multiple computational tools, with 12 significantly harmful variants N44H, S207C, N185S, and D84A exhibiting notable structural impacts. Docking studies with both wild-type and mutant forms of TLR4 tested 17 compounds, revealing Apigenin, GN8, SYUIQ-5, S-adenosylmethionine, Vixotrigine, and Tetracycline as potential inhibitors due to their strong affinities for TLR4. These findings suggest that these compounds may offer therapeutic potential for conjunctivitis, though further experimental validation is needed.

INTRODUCTION

Conjunctivitis is an inflammatory condition impacting the conjunctiva, the transparent membrane that covers the white of the eye and the inner eyelids. This condition is marked by symptoms such as excessive discharge, sensitivity

to light, redness of the conjunctiva, and itching. Conjunctivitis can be triggered by multiple factors, including allergens, viral agents, and bacterial infections [1]. A recent ophthalmology study in the USA highlights that eye diseases treated in emergency departments incur an annual cost of \$2

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billion. Conjunctivitis alone contributes around 28% of this total, underscoring the substantial financial strain eye conditions place on healthcare resources [2]. Conjunctivitis can be caused by several viral pathogens, including the varicella-zoster virus (VZV), herpes simplex virus (HSV) and adenovirus [3]. Fungi are significant contributors to eye infections, especially in tropical and developing regions. They can cause severe ocular candidiasis and keratitis, which may result in permanent vision loss [4]. Various bacteria, including Gram-positive types (*Staphylococcus aureus*, *Staphylococcus epidermidis*, *Streptococcus*, and *Bacillus* species), as well as Gram-negative (*Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Moraxella*, and *Haemophilus* spp.) often cause conjunctivitis and keratitis. They may enter the eye through skin contact, the respiratory tract, or external infection from another person [4, 5]. Genetic variants influencing angiogenic responsiveness, such as the pink-eyed mutation in the *oca2* gene, impact pink eye development in mice by altering angiogenesis. This mutation modifies blood vessel formation within the eye, contributing to changes associated with pink eye [6]. Allergic conjunctivitis is widespread, affecting between 15% and 40% of various populations. A study in Saudi Arabia found an age- and sex-adjusted prevalence of 70.5% among adults in the western region [7]. Pakistan reported 400,000 cases of viral conjunctivitis, with a particularly high surge in cases observed in Karachi [8]. Moreover, variants in the interleukin-4 gene (rs2243250) and its receptor (rs1805010) have been associated with viral conjunctivitis. Research has revealed significant differences in genotype distributions between viral conjunctivitis patients and healthy controls, suggesting these genetic variants may influence susceptibility to viral infections leading to conjunctivitis [9]. The genes associated with Herpes Simplex Virus Type 1 ocular infection include *UL24*, *UL29*

(*ICP8*), *UL41* (*VHS*), *UL53* (*gK*), *UL54* (*ICP27*), *UL56*, *ICP4*, *US1* (*ICP22*), *US3*, and *gG*, play critical roles in the virus's replication, immune evasion, and ocular tissue damage during infection [3]. Toll-like receptor 4 (*TLR4*) is significant in the innate immune response by recognizing pathogen-associated molecular patterns (PAMPs) and initiating inflammatory signaling pathways. In allergic conjunctivitis, *TLR4* can be activated by environmental allergens, such as pollen, dust mites, or pollutants, which are perceived as threats by the immune system [10]. The *TLR4* (ARMD10 or CD284) gene is located on chromosome 9q32 in humans and is composed of several exons and introns, which are transcribed into mRNA and subsequently translated into the *TLR4* protein. It spans multiple kilobases and is classified as a type I transmembrane protein, characterized by a single transmembrane domain that anchors it within the cell membrane. The extracellular domain of *TLR4* plays a key role in recognizing PAMPs, such as lipopolysaccharides (LPS), while the intracellular domain is involved in triggering signaling pathways [11]. The extracellular region of *TLR4* includes a leucine-rich repeat (LRR) motif, essential for binding ligands. This allows *TLR4* to identify specific molecular signatures from pathogens, including bacterial LPS, which activates an immune response. The intracellular portion contains the TIR domain, which is responsible for initiating downstream signaling after activation. The TIR domain interacts with adaptor proteins, including MyD88 and TRIF, leading to the activation of inflammatory pathways such as NF- κ B and MAPK, which ultimately results in the release of pro-inflammatory cytokines [12, 13]. Upon ligand binding, *TLR4* typically dimerizes, often in conjunction with the co-receptor MD-2, which is necessary for LPS and other PAMP recognition. The *TLR4* gene also undergoes alternative splicing, producing various isoforms that may have different functional

characteristics or tissue-specific expression. Genetic variations in the *TLR4* gene can alter its function and are linked to a range of conditions, including sepsis, autoimmune diseases, and allergic reactions [14].

Furthermore, *TLR4* expression was detected in circulating CD⁴⁺ T cells from individuals with chronic allergic conjunctivitis, and in conjunctival epithelial cells. The D299G (rs4986790) and T399I have been studied and 18% *TLR4* mutations, with a significantly higher incidence of gram-negative infections that may contribute to an increased susceptibility to allergic conjunctivitis [15, 16]. When peripheral blood mononuclear cells (PBMCs) from patients were stimulated with allergens such as Der p, a significant increase in both *TLR4* expression and activation markers (CD69) was observed in CD⁴⁺ T cells. This suggests that allergen-specific stimulation can enhance the *TLR4* activity, which may contribute to the Th2 inflammatory microenvironment commonly seen in allergic responses [15]. Bioinformatics tools play a crucial role in understanding the genetic foundations of infectious diseases, which is essential for early detection of eye infections and effective epidemiological responses. By utilizing a range of prediction tools, we categorized the nsSNPs in the *TLR4* gene and identified those most likely to disrupt receptor function, potentially leading to diseases such as conjunctivitis. Future research will focus on exploring the in-silico structural and functional effects of missense mutations in human *TLR4*, specifically with pink eye infections. This approach will aim to identify potential treatment targets and enhance drug precision. Such strategies hold promises for improving treatment efficacy and developing preventative measures to reduce infection rates.

1. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Screening datasets

The National Center for Biotechnology Information (NCBI) (<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov>) has made available the hTLR4 gene data, including unique SNP findings, through their dbSNP database (<http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/snp>). Additionally, UniProt (<https://www.uniprot.org>) is used to obtain protein sequence information, allowing for detailed insights into its structure and function. The Overall methodology of the present study is given in **Figure 1**.

Figure 1. Workflow of the current study

2.2 Prediction of nsSNPs

SNPNexus tool (<https://www.snp-nexus.org/v4>) simplifies the selection and prioritization of known and novel genomic variants [17]. Sorting Intolerant From Tolerant (SIFT) uses sequence homology to identify deleterious SNPs, analyzing amino acid variations that affect protein phenotypic and functional alterations [18]. PolyPhen analyzes protein composition and functionality by analyzing amino acid substitutions using protein sequence, and substitution information. The score ranges from 0.0 to 1.0 indicating deleterious or tolerated variants [19]. Protein Analysis through Evolutionary Relationship (PANTHER) (<https://www.pantherdb.org/tools>) uses evolutionary relationships and the Hidden Markov

Model (HMM) for analysis [20]. The *TLR4* sequence, mutant, and position are submitted to the query [21]. Amino acid substitutions on functional proteins are categorized as benign or harmful by the web server MutPred2 (<http://mutpred2.mutdb.org>), with "pathogenic mutation" values ranging from 0.5 to 1.0 [22]. Polyphen-2-Polymorphism Phenotyping v2 (<http://genetics.bwh.harvard.edu/pph2/>) predicts the consequence of an amino acid substitution on a protein's structure and, hence, function [23]. The PredictSNP

(<https://loschmidt.chemi.muni.cz/predictsnp1>) uses input data from various tools to predict the impact of changing one amino acid, offering increased effectiveness and accuracy [24].

2.3 Impact of disease-associated nsSNPs on protein stability.

SuSpect (<http://www.sbg.bio.ic.ac.uk/suspect>) analyzes disease prediction using sequence-based and annotation methods, reducing annotation bias and ranking genes based on multiple evidence lines [25]. SNPs & GO (<https://snps.biofold.org/snps-and-go/snps-and-go.html>) uses functional annotation of protein sequences to determine variation associated with a disease [22]. Meta SNP (<https://snps.biofold.org/meta-snp>) is used to predict a single nucleotide variation in protein sequence. The output value >0.5 is considered as a disease, and <0.5 is neutral. [26]. iStable (<http://predictor.nchu.edu.tw/iStable>) is a server that predicts protein stability changes using sequence or structure information, combining five forecasting instruments and a variety of feature coding and prediction techniques [27].

2.4 Homology Modeling Prediction

The SWISS-MODEL algorithm (<https://swissmodel.expasy.org>) is used for protein structural homology modeling that constructs accurate protein structures by utilizing closely related templates. The process begins by clustering

known protein structures and selecting the template with the highest sequence identity to the target protein [28]. Following model construction, SWISS-MODEL evaluates the model's quality using several validation metrics, including the Ramachandran plot, QMEAN score, and MolProbity score. These assessments provide insights into the geometric quality and reliability of the predicted structure [29].

2.5 Structural Verification Analysis

SAVESv6.1 (<https://saves.mbi.ucla.edu>) was used to select and validate a structural model, incorporating PROCHECK and ERRAT for overall quality. A RAMACHANDRAN plot assessed model quality, determining the amino acid preferred area and dihedral angle. This plot of the torsional angles phi (ϕ) and psi (ψ) of the residues (amino acids) contained in a peptide. By Ramachandran plot helps to determine which torsional angles are permitted and can obtain insight into the structure of peptides. The model with satisfying stereo-chemical quality was further assessed by QMEAN and ProSA was used to compute Z score values for the models [30].

2.6 Structural Superimposition

Template Modeling alignment (TM-Align) tool (<https://zhanggroup.org/TM-align>) used for comparing the structural similarities between wild-type and mutant protein models. It calculates the TM-score and Root Mean Square Deviation (RMSD) to assess the degree of structural divergence quantitatively [31]. In contrast, RMSD quantifies the average distance between corresponding atoms in the aligned proteins; higher RMSD values signify greater structural divergence [32].

2.7 Structural analysis of variants

Mutation 3D (<http://www.mutation3d.org/about.shtml>) is a valuable computational tool designed to analyze the effects of amino acid substitutions on protein models and structures. This platform facilitates the

identification of mutation clusters and functional hotspots, contributing to a deeper understanding of the implications of these alterations on protein function. The HOPE (Have (y) Our Protein Explained) program (<https://www3.cmbi.umcn.nl/hope/input>) collects details from multiple sources to offer insights into the effects of variants on *TLR4* structure. After the FASTA format is submitted, it finds the mutant residue and goes on to the following step of analysis [33].

2.8 Ligand Preparation

PubChem (<https://pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov>) is a comprehensive database that houses a wide range of chemical compounds, primarily small molecules, but also includes larger compounds such as lipids, peptides, carbohydrates, nucleotides, and chemically modified macromolecules. It provides detailed information on chemical structures, identifiers, chemical and physical properties, biological activities, patents, and health, safety, and toxicological data [34].

2.9 Molecular screening analysis

PyRx (<https://pyrx.sourceforge.io>) is a virtual screening tool used in computational drug discovery to evaluate libraries of compounds for potential therapeutic targets. It allows users to perform Virtual Screening on various platforms, guiding them through each step of the process from data preparation to job submission and result analysis. Discovery Studio Visualizer (<https://discover.3ds.com/discovery-studio-visualizer-download>) was then employed to examine the ligand-protein interactions, and both the ligand and protein structures were represented in 2D and 3D formats as PNG files for visualization. This workflow enables efficient drug discovery by predicting molecular interactions and identifying potential drug candidates [35].

RESULTS

3.1 Dataset download

In this study, a total of 8,702 SNPs of the human *TLR4* gene were downloaded from the dbNCBI database. These SNPs include 4,275 in UTR regions, with 3,824 located in the 3' UTR region and 451 in the 5' UTR region. There are also 15,843 SNPs in intronic regions, 799 synonymous variants, and 1,928 non-synonymous SNPs. Additionally, the dataset comprises 2,601 SNPs in the 3' downstream region, 2,902 SNPs in the 5' upstream region, 157 exonic mutations, and 208 SNPs in non-coding regions, as illustrated in **Figure 2**. For further analysis, the protein sequence of O00206 was retrieved from the UniProt database. The human *TLR4* gene is located in the 9q33.1 region of chromosome 9. It has a molecular weight of 95 kDa and consists of 4 exons and 10 distinct introns.

Figure 2. Bar Plot presents the SNPs in different regions of the *TLR4* Gene.

3.2 Functional Prediction of nsSNPs

A total of 8,702 rsIDs were submitted to SNPnexus, resulting in predictions for 1,724 variants, with 878 classified as deleterious and 972 as tolerated based on the SIFT algorithm (**Figure 3a**). Additionally, PolyPhen analysis revealed that 469 nsSNPs were likely to be damaging, 355 were categorized as possibly damaging, and 1,026 were identified as benign (**Figure 3b**). Among these, 132 SNPs were found to be common and were all predicted to be probably damaging (**Table 1**).

These findings highlight the potential significance of these variants in terms of their impact on protein function and their possible associations with disease.

Figure 3. Detrimental missense nsSNPs are predicted by a) SIFT algorithm 0 and b) PolyPhen

Table 1. Prediction of functional consequences of coding variants identified by SNPnexus

Variation ID	Mutation	Polyphen		SIFT		Variation ID	Mutation	Polyphen		SIFT	
		Score	Prediction	Score	Prediction			Score	Prediction	Score	Prediction
rs1383009042	P145L	0.911	PD	0	D	rs776282454	G699R	0.993	PD	0	D
rs755813457	I320T	0.911	PD	0	D	rs1157906794	G715V	0.993	PD	0	D
rs55786277	R804W	0.913	PD	0	D	rs200905500	R787H	0.993	PD	0	D
rs137853920	C281Y	0.915	PD	0	D	rs377719663	Y709C	0.994	PD	0.01	D
rs200246890	N205H	0.922	PD	0	D	rs892362464	L59M	0.995	PD	0	D
rs199930089	G715R	0.924	PD	0	D	rs201521400	F237L	0.996	PD	0	D
rs1044303225	V32A	0.929	PD	0	D	rs199763503	L658R	0.996	PD	0	D
rs1038463767	V735F	0.93	PD	0	D	rs1194635312	Y674C	0.996	PD	0	D
rs1416546558	N690S	0.932	PD	0.01	D	rs754642038	V736A	0.996	PD	0	D
rs773429738	L335I	0.933	PD	0	D	rs777803994	L802Q	0.996	PD	0	D
rs757953593	I247T	0.935	PD	0	D	rs1363147767	G252S	0.997	PD	0	D
rs1159116911	T151I	0.936	PD	0	D	rs1194292799	S455T	0.997	PD	0	D
rs201114738	S381G	0.939	PD	0	D	rs1194292799	S415T	0.997	PD	0	D
rs1163840909	E31V	0.94	PD	0	D	rs80197996	L470F	0.997	PD	0	D
rs370421152	V134L	0.94	PD	0	D	rs200787883	F492V	0.997	PD	0	D
rs762970720	V736L	0.946	PD	0	D	rs55905951	A676G	0.997	PD	0	D
rs1472004859	L117S	0.947	PD	0	D	rs761598705	H708R	0.997	PD	0	D
rs199666264	R257P	0.949	PD	0	D	rs750790595	R787C	0.997	PD	0.01	D
rs55799839	L260P	0.95	PD	0	D	rs769239861	R87S	0.998	PD	0	D
rs759420110	L571I	0.952	PD	0.01	D	rs56302444	I93V	0.998	PD	0.03	D
rs749872850	E685G	0.952	PD	0.01	D	rs370421152	V134M	0.998	PD	0	D
rs747209292	K694N	0.952	PD	0	D	rs188543451	L138P	0.998	PD	0	D
rs201835255	R257C	0.954	PD	0.01	D	rs993554067	L208F	0.998	PD	0	D
rs766151559	F516I	0.955	PD	0	D	rs2770145	C306W	0.998	PD	0	D
rs368003192	R810L	0.957	PD	0.01	D	rs770682940	N361K	0.998	PD	0.01	D
rs1235644534	N44H	0.961	PD	0	D	rs765968259	N721S	0.998	PD	0.02	D
rs769767782	V132L	0.964	PD	0.01	D	rs1258063271	A754V	0.998	PD	0	D

rs1301599599	V32M	0.965	PD	0.05	D	rs748382304	I769T	0.998	PD	0	D
rs199561420	S441L	0.965	PD	0	D	rs55751501	A814T	0.998	PD	0.01	D
rs56101219	I722V	0.968	PD	0	D	rs1301599599	V32L	0.999	PD	0.05	D
rs61734367	N361D	0.97	PD	0.01	D	rs201613484	L104F	0.999	PD	0	D
rs775401427	P49S	0.972	PD	0	D	rs200168998	I162T	0.999	PD	0	D
rs754342091	Y98C	0.972	PD	0	D	rs77214890	D181Y	0.999	PD	0	D
rs765289408	S105C	0.973	PD	0.03	D	rs759469467	I187S	0.999	PD	0	D
rs972966550	L511W	0.975	PD	0	D	rs1440077974	L233S	0.999	PD	0	D
rs1445128804	G765D	0.975	PD	0.01	D	rs777887873	L401Q	0.999	PD	0	D
rs1480203162	L375F	0.976	PD	0	D	rs777887873	L401P	0.999	PD	0	D
rs1480203162	L335F	0.976	PD	0	D	rs201792813	Y652C	0.999	PD	0	D
rs954875750	F237S	0.977	PD	0	D	rs751229651	V678A	0.999	PD	0	D
rs917000574	G279S	0.978	PD	0.01	D	rs751229651	V638A	0.999	PD	0	D
rs1256844267	T756P	0.979	PD	0	D	rs779420060	W687R	0.999	PD	0	D
rs780472681	S762I	0.979	PD	0.01	D	rs1174477453	V688L	0.999	PD	0	D
rs762746728	L307F	0.98	PD	0.03	D	rs1282672274	G699V	0.999	PD	0	D
rs1353182806	G726S	0.98	PD	0	D	rs56101219	I722F	0.999	PD	0	D
rs56380595	P823T	0.98	PD	0.02	D	rs746352626	G726D	0.999	PD	0	D
rs897794510	S207C	0.981	PD	0	D	rs746352626	G726V	0.999	PD	0	D
rs902036821	D194N	0.982	PD	0.02	D	rs1287623116	S744G	0.999	PD	0	D
rs1314441656	Q430P	0.983	PD	0	D	rs1048072828	T793A	0.999	PD	0	D
rs1216019140	C340W	0.984	PD	0	D	rs779025130	C40Y	1	PD	0	D
rs2770144	V310G	0.985	PD	0	D	rs868027365	D84N	1	PD	0	D
rs202114774	L519V	0.985	PD	0	D	rs760962514	D84A	1	PD	0	D
rs199632399	R745C	0.985	PD	0	D	rs1044303225	C88R	1	PD	0	D
rs766243776	N309Y	0.986	PD	0	D	rs766539584	L152V	1	PD	0	D
rs748810494	V134A	0.987	PD	0	D	rs537921846	N160S	1	PD	0	D
rs202040652	T793I	0.987	PD	0	D	rs1281579352	P168H	1	PD	0	D
rs199930089	G715S	0.988	PD	0	D	rs1296130154	N185S	1	PD	0	D
rs988829747	I742T	0.988	PD	0	D	rs371871286	N213K	1	PD	0	D
rs201897073	I146T	0.989	PD	0	D	rs371871286	N173K	1	PD	0	D
rs919321567	L372Q	0.989	PD	0.01	D	rs202089517	S407T	1	PD	0.04	D
rs1394250328	I742F	0.989	PD	0.01	D	rs934780727	N409S	1	PD	0	D
rs376443096	D428N	0.99	PD	0	D	rs764148809	L452R	1	PD	0	D
rs1382563975	V716M	0.99	PD	0	D	rs201456149	D453G	1	PD	0	D
rs373109368	L182V	0.992	PD	0.01	D	rs1285033378	C585Y	1	PD	0	D
rs1388911129	L779F	0.992	PD	0	D	rs1354283847	C609Y	1	PD	0	D
rs200139449	G803V	0.992	PD	0	D	rs1233324596	C609W	1	PD	0	D
rs1346126850	N481D	0.993	PD	0	D	rs200497661	R731Q	1	PD	0	D

***D**=Deleterious; **PD**= Probably Damaging

3.3 Prediction of functional impact of mutation

The analysis of nsSNPs using PANTHER, Predict SNP, and PolyPhen2 revealed significant insights

into their potential impact on protein function (Table 2). PANTHER classified 96 nsSNPs as Possibly Damaging, 28 as Probably Benign, and 8 as Probably Damaging, with specific mutations

(R810L, C306W, and L401Q) identified as likely impairing protein function. Predict SNP found 104 SNPs to have a detrimental effect and 28 to be neutral. PolyPhen2 predicted all 128 SNPs to be Probably Damaging, with a few exceptions, such as S415T, I769T, and P168H, which were

considered benign, and Y652C, which was marked as possibly damaging. These results suggest that many of the nsSNPs may have a detrimental effect on protein function, warranting further experimental investigation.

Table 2. List of disease linked variants predicted by computational tools.

Variation ID	Mutation	PANTHER		Polyphen2		Predict SNP
		Score	Prediction	Score	Prediction	Prediction
rs1383009042	P145L	0.5	Possibly Damaging	0.992	Probably Damaging	Neutral
rs755813457	I320T	0.19	Probably Benign	0.965	Probably Damaging	Deleterious
rs55786277	R804W	0.13	Probably Benign	0.999	Probably Damaging	Deleterious
rs137853920	C281Y	0.5	Possibly Damaging	0.998	Probably Damaging	Deleterious
rs200246890	N205H	0.5	Possibly Damaging	0.998	Probably Damaging	Deleterious
rs199930089	G715R	0.5	Possibly Damaging	0.992	Probably Damaging	Deleterious
rs1044303225	V32A	0.5	Possibly Damaging	1	Probably Damaging	Deleterious
rs1038463767	V735F	0.5	Possibly Damaging	0.986	Probably Damaging	Neutral
rs1416546558	N690S	0.27	Probably Benign	0.988	Probably Damaging	Neutral
rs773429738	L335I	0.5	Possibly Damaging	0.992	Probably Damaging	Neutral
rs757953593	I247T	0.5	Possibly Damaging	0.982	Probably Damaging	Neutral
rs1159116911	T151I	0.27	Probably Benign	0.965	Probably Damaging	Deleterious
rs201114738	S381G	0.5	Possibly Damaging	1	Probably Damaging	Neutral
rs1163840909	E31V	0.19	Probably Benign	0.801	Probably Damaging	Deleterious
rs370421152	V134L	0.5	Possibly Damaging	0.941	Probably Damaging	Neutral
rs762970720	V736L	0.5	Possibly Damaging	0.972	Probably Damaging	Deleterious
rs1472004859	L117S	0.5	Possibly Damaging	1	Probably Damaging	Deleterious
rs199666264	R257P	0.27	Probably Benign	1	Probably Damaging	Deleterious
rs55799839	L260P	0.5	Possibly Damaging	1	Probably Damaging	Deleterious
rs1235644534	N44H	0.13	Probably Benign	0.999	Probably Damaging	Deleterious
rs759420110	L571I	0.5	Possibly Damaging	0.992	Probably Damaging	Deleterious
rs749872850	E685G	0.5	Possibly Damaging	0.996	Probably Damaging	Deleterious
rs747209292	K694N	0.5	Possibly Damaging	0.996	Probably Damaging	Deleterious
rs201835255	R257C	0.27	Probably Benign	1	Probably Damaging	Deleterious
rs766151559	F516I	0.85	Possibly Damaging	0.998	Probably Damaging	Deleterious
rs368003192	R810L	0.5	Possibly Damaging	0.996	Probably Damaging	Deleterious
rs769767782	V132L	0.5	Possibly Damaging	0.979	Probably Damaging	Neutral
rs1301599599	V32M	0.27	Possibly Damaging	0.996	Probably Damaging	Deleterious
rs199561420	S441L	0.5	Probably Benign	0.972	Probably Damaging	Neutral
rs56101219	I722V	0.27	Possibly Damaging	0.994	Probably Damaging	Deleterious
rs61734367	N361D	0.5	Probably Benign	0.999	Probably Damaging	Deleterious
rs775401427	P49S	0.27	Possibly Damaging	1	Probably Damaging	Deleterious
rs754342091	Y98C	0.5	Probably Benign	1	Probably Damaging	Deleterious
rs765289408	S105C	0.19	Possibly Damaging	0.998	Probably Damaging	Deleterious
rs972966550	L511W	0.5	Probably Benign	0.996	Probably Damaging	Deleterious

rs1445128804	G765D	0.5	Possibly Damaging	0.996	Probably Damaging	Neutral
rs1480203162	L375F	0.5	Possibly Damaging	0.997	Probably Damaging	Deleterious
rs1480203162	L335F	0.5	Possibly Damaging	0.719	Probably Damaging	Deleterious
rs954875750	F237S	0.5	Possibly Damaging	1	Probably Damaging	Deleterious
rs917000574	G279S	0.5	Possibly Damaging	0.993	Probably Damaging	Neutral
rs1256844267	T756P	0.5	Possibly Damaging	0.999	Probably Damaging	Deleterious
rs780472681	S762I	0.5	Possibly Damaging	0.999	Probably Damaging	Deleterious
rs762746728	L307F	0.5	Possibly Damaging	0.995	Probably Damaging	Neutral
rs1353182806	G726S	0.5	Possibly Damaging	0.998	Probably Damaging	Neutral
rs56380595	P823T	0.27	Possibly Damaging	0.999	Probably Damaging	Neutral
rs897794510	S207C	0.5	Probably Benign	0.999	Probably Damaging	Deleterious
rs902036821	D194N	0.5	Possibly Damaging	0.978	Probably Damaging	Neutral
rs1314441656	Q430P	0.5	Possibly Damaging	1	Probably Damaging	Deleterious
rs1216019140	C340W	0.19	Possibly Damaging	0.997	Probably Damaging	Deleterious
rs2770144	V310G	0.5	Probably Benign	0.999	Probably Damaging	Deleterious
rs202114774	L519V	0.5	Possibly Damaging	0.999	Probably Damaging	Deleterious
rs199632399	R745C	0.5	Possibly Damaging	1	Probably Damaging	Deleterious
rs766243776	N309Y	0.5	Possibly Damaging	1	Probably Damaging	Deleterious
rs748810494	V134A	0.5	Possibly Damaging	1	Probably Damaging	Neutral
rs202040652	T793I	0.5	Possibly Damaging	0.999	Probably Damaging	Deleterious
rs199930089	G715S	0.27	Possibly Damaging	1	Probably Damaging	Deleterious
rs988829747	I742T	0.5	Probably Benign	0.999	Probably Damaging	Deleterious
rs201897073	I146T	0.5	Possibly Damaging	1	Probably Damaging	Deleterious
rs919321567	L372Q	0.27	Possibly Damaging	0.999	Probably Damaging	Deleterious
rs1394250328	I742F	0.5	Probably Benign	0.978	Probably Damaging	Neutral
rs376443096	D428N	0.5	Possibly Damaging	1	Probably Damaging	Neutral
rs1382563975	V716M	0.27	Possibly Damaging	1	Probably Damaging	Deleterious
rs373109368	L182V	0.5	Probably Benign	1	Probably Damaging	Deleterious
rs1388911129	L779F	0.27	Possibly Damaging	1	Probably Damaging	Deleterious
rs200139449	G803V	0.27	Probably Benign	1	Probably Damaging	Deleterious
rs1346126850	N481D	0.5	Probably Benign	0.999	Probably Damaging	Deleterious
rs776282454	G699R	0.5	Possibly Damaging	1	Probably Damaging	Deleterious
rs1157906794	G715V	0.5	Possibly Damaging	1	Probably Damaging	Deleterious
rs200905500	R787H	0.5	Possibly Damaging	1	Probably Damaging	Deleterious
rs377719663	Y709C	0.5	Possibly Damaging	1	Probably Damaging	Deleterious
rs892362464	L59M	0.5	Possibly Damaging	1	Probably Damaging	Deleterious
rs201521400	F237L	0.5	Possibly Damaging	1	Probably Damaging	Deleterious
rs199763503	L658R	0.5	Possibly Damaging	1	Probably Damaging	Deleterious
rs1194635312	Y674C	0.5	Possibly Damaging	1	Probably Damaging	Neutral
rs754642038	V736A	0.27	Possibly Damaging	1	Probably Damaging	Neutral
rs777803994	L802Q	0.5	Probably Benign	1	Probably Damaging	Deleterious
rs1363147767	G252S	0.5	Possibly Damaging	1	Probably Damaging	Neutral
rs1194292799	S455T	0.27	Possibly Damaging	0	Probably Damaging	Deleterious

rs1194292799	S415T	0.27	Probably Benign	1	Benign	Deleterious
rs80197996	L470F	0.5	Probably Benign	1	Probably Damaging	Deleterious
rs200787883	F492V	0.5	Possibly Damaging	1	Probably Damaging	Deleterious
rs55905951	A676G	0.5	Possibly Damaging	1	Probably Damaging	Deleterious
rs761598705	H708R	0.5	Possibly Damaging	1	Probably Damaging	Neutral
rs750790595	R787C	0.5	Possibly Damaging	0.999	Probably Damaging	Neutral
rs769239861	R87S	0.5	Possibly Damaging	1	Probably Damaging	Deleterious
rs56302444	I93V	0.5	Possibly Damaging	1	Probably Damaging	Deleterious
rs370421152	V134M	0.27	Possibly Damaging	1	Probably Damaging	Deleterious
rs188543451	L138P	0.5	Probably Benign	1	Probably Damaging	Deleterious
rs993554067	L208F	0.74	Possibly Damaging	0.999	Probably Damaging	Deleterious
rs2770145	C306W	0.27	Probably Damaging	1	Probably Damaging	Deleterious
rs770682940	N361K	0.5	Probably Benign	0.999	Probably Damaging	Deleterious
rs765968259	N721S	0.5	Possibly Damaging	1	Probably Damaging	Deleterious
rs1258063271	A754V	0.5	Possibly Damaging	0.126	Probably Damaging	Deleterious
rs748382304	I769T	0.5	Possibly Damaging	1	Benign	Neutral
rs55751501	A814T	0.5	Possibly Damaging	1	Probably Damaging	Deleterious
rs1301599599	V32L	0.74	Possibly Damaging	1	Probably Damaging	Deleterious
rs201613484	L104F	0.5	Probably Damaging	1	Probably Damaging	Deleterious
rs200168998	I162T	0.27	Possibly Damaging	1	Probably Damaging	Deleterious
rs77214890	D181Y	0.5	Probably Benign	1	Probably Damaging	Deleterious
rs759469467	I187S	0.27	Possibly Damaging	1.000	Probably Damaging	Deleterious
rs1440077974	L233S	0.74	Probably Benign	1	Probably Damaging	Deleterious
rs777887873	L401Q	0.74	Probably Damaging	1	Probably Damaging	Deleterious
rs777887873	L401P	0.5	Probably Damaging	0.534	Probably Damaging	Deleterious
rs201792813	Y652C	0.5	Possibly Damaging	1	Possibly Damaging	Neutral
rs751229651	V678A	0.27	Possibly Damaging	1	Probably Damaging	Deleterious
rs751229651	V638A	0.5	Probably Benign	1	Probably Damaging	Deleterious
rs779420060	W687R	0.5	Possibly Damaging	1	Probably Damaging	Deleterious
rs1174477453	V688L	0.5	Possibly Damaging	1	Probably Damaging	Deleterious
rs1282672274	G699V	0.5	Possibly Damaging	1	Probably Damaging	Deleterious
rs56101219	I722F	0.5	Possibly Damaging	1	Probably Damaging	Deleterious
rs746352626	G726D	0.5	Possibly Damaging	1	Probably Damaging	Deleterious
rs746352626	G726V	0.5	Possibly Damaging	1.000	Probably Damaging	Deleterious
rs1287623116	S744G	0.5	Possibly Damaging	1	Probably Damaging	Neutral
rs1048072828	T793A	0.5	Possibly Damaging	1	Probably Damaging	Deleterious
rs779025130	C40Y	0.5	Possibly Damaging	1	Probably Damaging	Deleterious
rs868027365	D84N	0.5	Possibly Damaging	1	Probably Damaging	Deleterious
rs760962514	D84A	0.5	Possibly Damaging	1	Probably Damaging	Deleterious
rs1044303225	C88R	0.5	Possibly Damaging	1	Probably Damaging	Deleterious
rs766539584	L152V	0.74	Possibly Damaging	1	Probably Damaging	Deleterious
rs537921846	N160S	0.5	Possibly Damaging	0.258	Probably Damaging	Deleterious
rs1281579352	P168H	0.5	Possibly Damaging	0.999	Benign	Neutral

rs1296130154	N185S	0.74	Possibly Damaging	1	Probably Damaging	Deleterious
rs371871286	N213K	0.27	Probably Damaging	1	Probably Damaging	Deleterious
rs371871286	N173K	0.5	Probably Benign	1	Probably Damaging	Deleterious
rs202089517	S407T	0.74	Possibly Damaging	1	Probably Damaging	Deleterious
rs934780727	N409S	0.5	Probably Damaging	1	Probably Damaging	Deleterious
rs764148809	L452R	0.5	Possibly Damaging	1	Probably Damaging	Deleterious
rs201456149	D453G	0.5	Possibly Damaging	1	Probably Damaging	Deleterious
rs1285033378	C585Y	0.5	Possibly Damaging	1	Probably Damaging	Deleterious
rs1354283847	C609Y	0.5	Possibly Damaging	1	Probably Damaging	Deleterious
rs1233324596	C609W	0.5	Possibly Damaging	1	Probably Damaging	Deleterious
rs200497661	R731Q	0.5	Possibly Damaging	0.877	Probably Damaging	Neutral

1.4 Association of nsSNPs with disease

Using SNP &Go, SuSpect, and Meta SNP, the phenotypic impact of nsSNPs on the *TLR4* gene was predicted (Table 3). SNP &Go identified 118 substitutions as neutral and 14 as disease-associated. The Meta SNP server also linked 90 SNPs to diseases and identified 42 as neutral. SuSpect predicted 132 nsSNPs as disease-causing. Any SNP marked as neutral by these tools was

excluded from further analysis. Functional analysis of the remaining 132 nsSNPs showed that they have deleterious, probably damaging, or disease-causing effects on the *TLR4* protein. Using the i-stable tool, which assesses changes in protein thermal stability, 111 SNPs were found to reduce stability, while 21 SNPs showed an increase in stability.

Table 3. Prediction of disease associated nsSNPs and Protein Stability change prediction

Variation ID	Mutation	SNP & GO	SuSpect		Meta SNP		i stable	
		Score	Effect	Score	Score	Effect	Stability	Conf. score
rs1383009042	P145L	9	Neutral	54	0	Neutral	Decrease	0.800778
rs755813457	I320T	9	Neutral	88	3	Neutral	Decrease	0.875835
rs55786277	R804W	1	Neutral	85	6	Disease	Decrease	0.735661
rs137853920	C281Y	6	Neutral	79	5	Neutral	Increase	0.761752
rs200246890	N205H	10	Neutral	70	1	Neutral	Decrease	0.807955
rs199930089	G715R	2	Disease	91	9	Disease	Increase	0.59246
rs1044303225	V32A	9	Neutral	42	6	Neutral	Decrease	0.831297
rs1038463767	V735F	7	Neutral	78	1	Disease	Decrease	0.862233
rs1416546558	N690S	8	Neutral	60	0	Neutral	Decrease	0.889097
rs773429738	L335I	6	Neutral	77	1	Neutral	Increase	0.519921
rs757953593	I247T	8	Neutral	77	7	Neutral	Decrease	0.824498
rs1159116911	T151I	8	Neutral	84	2	Neutral	Decrease	0.82995
rs201114738	S381G	9	Neutral	79	0	Neutral	Decrease	0.863368
rs1163840909	E31V	9	Neutral	54	5	Neutral	Decrease	0.838044
rs370421152	V134L	9	Neutral	49	2	Neutral	Decrease	0.509748
rs762970720	V736L	7	Neutral	89	2	Neutral	Decrease	0.86035
rs1472004859	L117S	5	Neutral	81	1	Disease	Decrease	0.835144
rs199666264	R257P	4	Neutral	68	3	Disease	Decrease	0.758715

rs55799839	L260P	4	Neutral	59	0	Disease	Decrease	0.783652
rs1235644534	N44H	8	Neutral	62	1	Disease	Decrease	0.847527
rs759420110	L571I	7	Neutral	55	1	Neutral	Decrease	0.605933
rs749872850	E685G	5	Neutral	83	4	Disease	Decrease	0.895556
rs747209292	K694N	6	Neutral	77	0	Disease	Decrease	0.810386
rs201835255	R257C	6	Neutral	65	0	Disease	Decrease	0.764912
rs766151559	F516I	5	Neutral	91	1	Disease	Decrease	0.530973
rs368003192	R810L	1	Neutral	88	4	Disease	Decrease	0.723851
rs769767782	V132L	8	Neutral	52	2	Neutral	Decrease	0.907118
rs1301599599	V32M	9	Neutral	42	6	Neutral	Decrease	0.814225
rs199561420	S441L	8	Neutral	62	0	Neutral	Increase	0.767198
rs56101219	I722V	9	Neutral	83	0	Neutral	Decrease	0.857769
rs61734367	N361D	8	Neutral	83	3	Neutral	Increase	0.575585
rs775401427	P49S	6	Neutral	93	4	Disease	Decrease	0.76392
rs754342091	Y98C	5	Neutral	59	3	Disease	Increase	0.801449
rs765289408	S105C	7	Neutral	86	4	Disease	Increase	0.60583
rs972966550	L511W	8	Neutral	93	3	Disease	Decrease	0.570666
rs1445128804	G765D	6	Neutral	46	0	Disease	Decrease	0.824948
rs1480203162	L375F	9	Neutral	93	1	Neutral	Decrease	0.780765
rs1480203162	L335F	6	Neutral	88	1	Disease	Decrease	0.873495
rs954875750	F237S	7	Neutral	62	1	Disease	Decrease	0.782778
rs917000574	G279S	9	Neutral	48	4	Neutral	Decrease	0.829709
rs1256844267	T756P	0	Disease	76	6	Disease	Decrease	0.776527
rs780472681	S762I	3	Neutral	64	5	Disease	Increase	0.861936
rs762746728	L307F	8	Neutral	71	6	Neutral	Decrease	0.764051
rs1353182806	G726S	6	Neutral	52	0	Neutral	Decrease	0.726902
rs56380595	P823T	5	Neutral	45	2	Disease	Decrease	0.829011
rs897794510	S207C	9	Neutral	71	2	Disease	Increase	0.521313
rs902036821	D194N	8	Neutral	68	7	Neutral	Decrease	0.794228
rs1314441656	Q430P	7	Neutral	65	5	Disease	Decrease	0.758183
rs1216019140	C340W	7	Neutral	85	5	Disease	Decrease	0.53435
rs2770144	V310G	7	Neutral	74	2	Disease	Decrease	0.872542
rs202114774	L519V	9	Neutral	92	1	Neutral	Decrease	0.75702
rs199632399	R745C	3	Neutral	73	6	Disease	Decrease	0.82176
rs766243776	N309Y	7	Neutral	84	1	Disease	Increase	0.580148
rs748810494	V134A	9	Neutral	41	4	Neutral	Decrease	0.843255
rs202040652	T793I	1	Neutral	88	0	Neutral	Decrease	0.769871
rs199930089	G715S	0	Neutral	92	7	Disease	Decrease	0.767046
rs988829747	I742T	4	Neutral	90	3	Disease	Decrease	0.803838
rs201897073	I146T	7	Neutral	85	2	Disease	Decrease	0.868333
rs919321567	L372Q	8	Neutral	95	3	Disease	Decrease	0.662393
rs1394250328	I742F	2	Neutral	77	2	Disease	Decrease	0.788934

rs376443096	D428N	9	Neutral	54	6	Neutral	Increase	0.531709
rs1382563975	V716M	7	Neutral	58	1	Disease	Decrease	0.777009
rs373109368	L182V	8	Neutral	92	1	Neutral	Decrease	0.790967
rs1388911129	L779F	8	Neutral	89	2	Disease	Decrease	0.833589
rs200139449	G803V	4	Neutral	51	4	Disease	Decrease	0.556804
rs1346126850	N481D	4	Neutral	97	5	Disease	Decrease	0.644177
rs776282454	G699R	7	Neutral	27	4	Disease	Decrease	0.788658
rs1157906794	G715V	1	Disease	88	8	Disease	Decrease	0.531214
rs200905500	R787H	6	Neutral	69	3	Disease	Decrease	0.875812
rs377719663	Y709C	4	Neutral	87	6	Disease	Decrease	0.861331
rs892362464	L59M	8	Neutral	97	2	Disease	Decrease	0.835298
rs201521400	F237L	9	Neutral	57	1	Neutral	Decrease	0.761194
rs199763503	L658R	0	Disease	65	4	Disease	Decrease	0.856749
rs1194635312	Y674C	0	Disease	79	7	Disease	Decrease	0.759093
rs754642038	V736A	4	Neutral	98	3	Disease	Decrease	0.863389
rs777803994	L802Q	5	Neutral	24	0	Neutral	Decrease	0.847852
rs1363147767	G252S	9	Neutral	37	7	Neutral	Decrease	0.804551
rs1194292799	S455T	6	Neutral	72	0	Disease	Decrease	0.779176
rs1194292799	S415T	9	Neutral	52	5	Neutral	Increase	0.709602
rs80197996	L470F	4	Neutral	83	2	Disease	Decrease	0.652258
rs200787883	F492V	3	Neutral	95	3	Disease	Increase	0.603573
rs55905951	A676G	6	Neutral	79	2	Disease	Decrease	0.808704
rs761598705	H708R	0	Disease	90	6	Disease	Increase	0.697562
rs750790595	R787C	2	Neutral	80	5	Disease	Decrease	0.858065
rs769239861	R87S	8	Neutral	37	1	Neutral	Decrease	0.702746
rs56302444	I93V	9	Neutral	89	4	Neutral	Decrease	0.884007
rs370421152	V134M	9	Neutral	46	2	Neutral	Decrease	0.826485
rs188543451	L138P	1	Neutral	97	5	Disease	Decrease	0.806341
rs993554067	L208F	6	Neutral	81	2	Disease	Decrease	0.604569
rs2770145	C306W	7	Neutral	66	0	Disease	Decrease	0.751925
rs770682940	N361K	6	Neutral	87	1	Disease	Decrease	0.66961
rs765968259	N721S	6	Neutral	81	2	Disease	Decrease	0.554849
rs1258063271	A754V	3	Neutral	94	3	Disease	Decrease	0.801621
rs748382304	I769T	4	Neutral	98	5	Disease	Decrease	0.812199
rs55751501	A814T	6	Neutral	90	2	Disease	Decrease	0.872272
rs1301599599	V32L	9	Neutral	39	7	Neutral	Decrease	0.675548
rs201613484	L104F	8	Neutral	99	5	Disease	Decrease	0.846026
rs200168998	I162T	6	Neutral	95	4	Disease	Decrease	0.763441
rs77214890	D181Y	7	Neutral	75	2	Disease	Increase	0.664035
rs759469467	I187S	2	Neutral	97	3	Disease	Decrease	0.885339
rs1440077974	L233S	5	Neutral	83	2	Disease	Decrease	0.878476
rs777887873	L401Q	3	Neutral	98	5	Disease	Decrease	0.800966

rs777887873	L401P	1	Disease	98	5	Disease	Decrease	0.800863
rs201792813	Y652C	3	Neutral	85	7	Disease	Decrease	0.773517
rs751229651	V678A	1	Neutral	91	5	Disease	Increase	0.576001
rs751229651	V638A	8	Neutral	59	1	Neutral	Decrease	0.85106
rs779420060	W687R	2	Neutral	96	9	Disease	Decrease	0.798396
rs1174477453	V688L	5	Neutral	90	2	Disease	Decrease	0.735517
rs1282672274	G699V	4	Neutral	59	4	Disease	Decrease	0.810926
rs56101219	I722F	2	Neutral	93	5	Disease	Decrease	0.841606
rs746352626	G726D	1	Neutral	88	6	Disease	Decrease	0.6951
rs746352626	G726V	3	Neutral	70	4	Disease	Decrease	0.697765
rs1287623116	S744G	5	Neutral	93	5	Disease	Decrease	0.82433
rs1048072828	T793A	4	Neutral	92	2	Disease	Decrease	0.792187
rs779025130	C40Y	5	Disease	96	6	Disease	Increase	0.651774
rs868027365	D84N	8	Neutral	71	0	Neutral	Decrease	0.710009
rs760962514	D84A	6	Neutral	90	3	Disease	Decrease	0.66321
rs1044303225	C88R	6	Disease	96	8	Disease	Increase	0.5
rs766539584	L152V	7	Neutral	94	0	Neutral	Decrease	0.835198
rs537921846	N160S	2	Neutral	98	3	Disease	Increase	0.61148
rs1281579352	P168H	7	Neutral	73	3	Disease	Decrease	0.811214
rs1296130154	N185S	4	Neutral	98	0	Disease	Decrease	0.805635
rs371871286	N213K	6	Neutral	88	3	Disease	Increase	0.593595
rs371871286	N173K	9	Neutral	73	1	Neutral	Decrease	0.781762
rs202089517	S407T	9	Neutral	63	6	Neutral	Decrease	0.672228
rs934780727	N409S	5	Neutral	94	1	Disease	Decrease	0.8161
rs764148809	L452R	1	Disease	92	5	Disease	Decrease	0.817242
rs201456149	D453G	1	Neutral	86	2	Disease	Decrease	0.759654
rs1285033378	C585Y	5	Disease	99	9	Disease	Increase	0.791755
rs1354283847	C609Y	3	Disease	98	9	Disease	Decrease	0.709539
rs1233324596	C609W	4	Disease	98	9	Disease	Decrease	0.693086
rs200497661	R731Q	3	Disease	91	4	Disease	Decrease	0.804204

Additionally, a comparison of 82 highly conserved mutations in *TLR4* proteins was conducted using 10 bioinformatic tools to identify potential conformational changes (**Table 4**). These analyses provide valuable insights into the potential effects of these SNPs on the *TLR4* protein and its function.

Figure 4. 3D Model of *TLR4* gene

3.5 Homology modeling and validation of structure

The 3D model of the *TLR4* protein was created using a template from the Swiss Model, as the PDB model with ID 5NAO was not fully available. The Swiss Model identified 50 templates, with a 99.64% sequence identity to the query sequence, corresponding to the STML ID Q9TTN0.1.A. This template was used to construct a more complete model of *TLR4*, focusing on the sequence from amino acids 1 to 839. Specifically, the AlphaFold DB model of TLR4_PANPA (gene: TLR4, organism: Pan paniscus) was used for the query sequence. The model's quality and the resulting structure, created using PyMol, are displayed in **Figure 4**. This 3D model provides a more accurate representation of the *TLR4* protein, allowing for further investigation into the impact of mutations on its stability. The *TLR4* protein model was

refined using GalaxyRefine, resulting in the selection of model 05 as the most refined version. The model's quality was evaluated using QMEAN, yielding a Z-score of -0.81, and a ProSA score was -7.51, both of which were compared to experimental structures of similar size. The final structure adhered to all potential energy calculation constraints, with the majority of amino acid residues (99.64%) located in favorable regions of the RAMACHANDRAN plot. A negative QMEAN Z-score suggests that the protein structure may be unstable. In **Figure 5**, the refined *TLR4* model is highlighted with a red star, indicating its significance and the structural assessment based on these quality metrics. These findings suggest that while the model is refined, it may require further investigation to confirm its stability.

Figure 5. Procheck-RAMACHANDRAN plot (a). QMEAN of the native *TLR4* predicted model (b) ProSA plot.

The E31V, R257P, L260P, N44H, R257C, P49S, F237S, S207C, I146T, L182V, L59M, L138P, L208F, I162T, D181Y, I187S, L233S, C40Y, D84A, C88R, N160S, N185S, N213K showed high RMSD values, indicating significant structural changes. SAVES was used to validate

the modeled structures, and a RAMACHANDRAN plot analysis was performed to assess the secondary structure of the proteins. The full set of predicted outcomes, including specific details, is provided in **Table 2**. These results indicate that the modeled mutant proteins

are structurally sound, with the majority of residues occupying stable conformations.

Table 4. Structural validation and comparison of *TLR4* gene

Variation ID	Mutation	ERRAT	Procheck		Verify	TM Align	
		Score	Core	Allow	Score	Tm Score	RMSD
Model		92.3274	0.825	0.152	0.7521		
rs755813457	I320T	88.8748	0.9	0.095	0.7402	0.99852	0.38
rs55786277	R804W	88.539	0.895	0.096	0.7271	0.99845	0.39
rs199930089	G715R	88.0503	0.889	0.105	0.7437	0.99821	0.42
rs1159116911	T151I	91.2989	0.887	0.104	0.7652	0.99842	0.39
rs1163840909	E31V	88.7768	0.896	0.096	0.7664	0.99849	0.38
rs1472004859	L117S	89.8862	0.899	0.093	0.7509	0.99843	0.39
rs199666264	R257P	90.0504	0.89	0.1	0.7449	0.99842	0.39
rs55799839	L260P	86.22	0.901	0.092	0.7521	0.99841	0.39
rs1235644534	N44H	87.8635	0.897	0.093	0.7735	0.99832	0.41
rs749872850	E685G	91.1504	0.893	0.1	0.7342	0.99837	0.4
rs747209292	K694N	91.5723	0.89	0.105	0.7485	0.99846	0.39
rs201835255	R257C	90.6566	0.89	0.103	0.7318	0.99854	0.38
rs766151559	F516I	92.9114	0.886	0.102	0.7592	0.99851	0.38
rs368003192	R810L	89.029	0.894	0.098	0.7461	0.99824	0.42
rs775401427	P49S	90.2408	0.897	0.096	0.7735	0.99838	0.4
rs754342091	Y98C	89.1414	0.892	0.096	0.7449	0.99839	0.4
rs972966550	L511W	89.3805	0.891	0.098	0.758	0.99841	0.39
rs1480203162	L335F	88.6076	0.894	0.098	0.7592	0.99837	0.4
rs954875750	F237S	87.6106	0.891	0.102	0.7557	0.99842	0.39
rs1256844267	T756P	90.7828	0.898	0.091	0.7497	0.99837	0.4
rs897794510	S207C	90.4403	0.894	0.099	0.7461	0.99828	0.41
rs1314441656	Q430P	87.9093	0.886	0.102	0.7557	0.99831	0.41
rs1216019140	C340W	90.2408	0.891	0.1	0.7449	0.99835	0.4
rs2770144	V310G	85.7503	0.894	0.097	0.7664	0.99835	0.4
rs199632399	R745C	89.3671	0.904	0.088	0.764	0.99847	0.39
rs199930089	G715S	88.1313	0.887	0.105	0.7461	0.9983	0.41
rs988829747	I742T	85.335	0.887	0.105	76.52%	0.99834	0.4
rs201897073	I146T	90.404	0.894	0.101	75.21%	0.99837	0.4
rs919321567	L372Q	88.5101	0.898	0.097	0.7712	0.99836	0.4
rs1394250328	I742F	90.4282	0.894	0.096	0.7557	0.99843	0.39
rs1382563975	V716M	87.3897	0.903	0.091	0.7747	0.99843	0.39
rs373109368	L182V	89.3671	0.891	0.1	0.7676	0.99836	0.4
rs1388911129	L779F	90.1141	0.899	0.092	0.7497	0.9984	0.4
rs200139449	G803V	90.5303	0.893	0.101	0.7485	0.99848	0.38
rs1346126850	N481D	90.7712	0.886	0.105	0.7592	0.99835	0.4
rs776282454	G699R	90.7945	0.898	0.092	0.7676	0.99847	0.39
rs1157906794	G715V	88.7768	0.9	0.094	0.7616	0.99836	0.4
rs200905500	R787H	87.6419	0.889	0.106	0.7783	0.99838	0.4

rs377719663	Y709C	88.3838	0.887	0.102	0.7652	0.99839	0.4
rs892362464	L59M	88.3692	0.889	0.101	0.7342	0.99839	0.4
rs199763503	L658R	90.3676	0.89	0.102	0.7569	0.9985	0.38
rs1194635312	Y674C	89.0428	0.898	0.097	0.7485	0.99845	0.39
rs777803994	L802Q	89.8734	0.891	0.098	0.7426	0.99839	0.4
rs1194292799	S455T	88.1013	0.887	0.101	0.7652	0.99837	0.4
rs80197996	L470F	89.5202	0.894	0.093	0.7414	0.99835	0.4
rs55905951	A676G	87.3578	0.894	0.097	0.764	0.99846	0.39
rs188543451	L138P	87.6904	0.896	0.093	0.7664	0.99841	0.39
rs993554067	L208F	90.4943	0.892	0.1	0.7533	0.99833	0.4
rs2770145	C306W	90.9091	0.896	0.096	0.7473	0.99854	0.38
rs770682940	N361K	90.3797	0.9	0.091	0.7509	0.99853	0.38
rs765968259	N721S	88.5932	0.896	0.095	0.7569	0.99833	0.4
rs1258063271	A754V	89.7856	0.894	0.1	0.7664	0.99833	0.4
rs55751501	A814T	89.8515	0.892	0.101	0.745	0.97484	0.8
rs201613484	L104F	92.0354	0.894	0.101	0.7676	0.99833	0.4
rs200168998	I162T	90.2532	0.885	0.106	0.7569	0.99852	0.38
rs77214890	D181Y	88.8466	0.883	0.108	0.7878	0.99851	0.38
rs759469467	I187S	90.5542	0.896	0.093	0.7604	0.99834	0.4
rs1440077974	L233S	88.0503	0.903	0.085	0.7723	0.99846	0.39
rs777887873	L401Q	86.185	0.891	0.101	0.7437	0.99839	0.4
rs777887873	L401P	89.2132	0.891	0.1	0.7604	0.99851	0.38
rs751229651	V638A	89.2677	0.899	0.097	0.7533	0.99835	0.4
rs779420060	W687R	89.0013	0.889	0.104	0.7521	0.99835	0.4
rs1174477453	V688L	89.2541	0.899	0.093	74.85%	0.99848	0.39
rs1282672274	G699V	89.0704	0.895	0.098	0.7545	0.99831	0.41
rs56101219	I722F	89.2405	0.894	0.097	0.7652	0.99837	0.4
rs746352626	G726D	91.7513	0.895	0.096	0.733	0.99848	0.38
rs746352626	G726V	90.3023	0.898	0.094	0.7414	0.99828	0.41
rs1048072828	T793A	88.2724	0.891	0.101	0.7604	0.99857	0.37
rs779025130	C40Y	86.6162	0.895	0.096	0.7616	0.99838	0.4
rs760962514	D84A	89.029	0.891	0.104	0.7807	0.9983	0.41
rs1044303225	C88R	90.2655	0.894	0.096	0.7664	0.99835	0.4
rs537921846	N160S	89.2541	0.891	0.102	0.7557	0.99838	0.4
rs1296130154	N185S	89.4207	0.891	0.098	0.7545	0.99828	0.41
rs371871286	N213K	87.6263	0.896	0.097	0.7664	0.9983	0.41
rs371871286	N173K	85.8407	0.883	0.106	0.7449	0.99845	0.39
rs934780727	N409S	86.9289	0.89	0.104	0.7533	0.99859	0.37
rs764148809	L452R	88.0051	0.882	0.108	0.7497	0.99832	0.41
rs201456149	D453G	85.5528	0.887	0.105	0.7688	0.99844	0.39
rs1285033378	C585Y	89.0428	0.891	0.098	0.7426	0.99834	0.4
rs1354283847	C609Y	85.9316	0.891	0.1	0.7461	0.99854	0.38
rs1233324596	C609W	90.621	0.899	0.091	0.7878	0.99845	0.39
rs200497661	R731Q	90.2655	0.887	0.102	0.7497	0.99851	0.38

3.6 Structural effect of mutations

Mutation 3D predicts the potential impact of amino acid substitutions on protein structures, as outlined in **Table 5**. Mutations that are clustered are represented in red, while covered mutations are

shown in blue. This visualization helps to distinguish the different types of mutations based on their location and potential structural consequences.

Table 5. Functional prediction of *TLR4* protein by Mutation 3D

Variation ID	Mutation	Mutation 3D Prediction
rs1163840909	E31V	Covered
rs199666264	R257P	Clustered
rs55799839	L260P	Clustered
rs1235644534	N44H	Covered
rs201835255	R257C	Clustered
rs775401427	P49S	Covered
rs954875750	F237S	Clustered
rs897794510	S207C	Clustered
rs201897073	I146T	Clustered
rs373109368	L182V	Clustered
rs892362464	L59M	Covered
rs188543451	L138P	Covered
rs993554067	L208F	Clustered
rs200168998	I162T	Covered
rs77214890	D181Y	Clustered
rs759469467	I187S	Covered
rs1440077974	L233S	Clustered
rs779025130	C40Y	Covered
rs760962514	D84A	Covered
rs1044303225	C88R	Covered
rs537921846	N160S	Clustered
rs1296130154	N185S	Clustered
rs371871286	N213K	Clustered

Moreover, HOPE predicted the impact of 12 variants on the hydrophobicity, spatial structure, physical and chemical characteristics, and function of the KRT74 protein. According to HOPE, the mutant residue N44H is larger than the wild-type residue, while the mutant residues D84A and N185S are smaller than the wild-type. The effect

of the D84A mutation on the protein is considered probably damaging. The location of the N44H mutation is within the protein's domain, while D84A is located in or near highly conserved regions. The S207C mutation is found at homologous sequences, and its effect is predicted to be possibly damaging (**Figure 6**).

Figure 6. Structural changes of mutant highlighted by HOPE Project.

3.7 Protein-ligand docking analysis

PyRx program utilized molecular docking to examine ligand-protein interactions, docking 16 selected ligands with *TLR4*. The binding affinities of these ligands correlate with their activity levels, and all 16 compounds with their respective binding affinities are listed in **Table 6**. From this, 5 compounds with strong binding affinities (high

binding scores) Apigenin, Tetracycline, Tetrodotoxin, S-adenosylmethionine, and Vixotrigine were selected and docked with the native *TLR4* protein. For further analysis, Discovery Studio was used, which provides a two-dimensional representation of each docking interaction.

Table 6. Interpretation of docking score highlighted by PyRx between ligands and native protein.

Ligands	Model	Ligands	Model
Apigenin	-6.5	SYUIQ-5	-6.1
GAG	-4.8	Tamoxifen	-5.7
GN8	-5.9	Tetrodotoxin	-6.4
Riluzole	-4.9	S-adenosylmethionine	-6.3
Sclareol	-5.3	Vixotrigine	-7.1
Statin	-5.5	Topiramate	-5.5
Sinularin	-5.8	Thymol	-4.7
Tetracycline	-7	Thymoquione	-4.9

Every ligand selected for docking had a binding free energy greater than -4 kcal/mol, as shown in **Table 4**. The highest binding energy revealed that the *TLR4* protein was successfully docked with Vixotrigine. Vixotrigine and Tetracycline showed the highest binding affinities of -7.1 and -7.0 kcal/mol, respectively, which exceed the affinities

of conventional ligand-binding. The Apigenin ligand was fixed in the *TLR4* binding pocket sites through conventional Van der Waals interactions with TYR403, GLU376, ARG355, GLU425, ILE450, and TYR451. The Tetracycline ligand was fixed in the *TLR4* binding pocket sites through Van der Waals interactions with ASN433,

HIS458, THR457, THR459, MET437, LYS435, GLU439, and ALA465. The Tetrodotoxin ligand was fixed in the TLR4 binding pocket sites via Van der Waals interactions with ALA462, MET437, SER438, LEU434, ASN433, GLU439, THR457, and THR459. The S-adenosylmethionine ligand was fixed in the TLR4 binding pocket sites via Van der Waals interactions with ALA610, ASN554, PHE581, LEU553, ARG606, and GLN505. The Vixotrigine ligand was fixed in the TLR4 binding

pocket sites through Van der Waals interactions with MET607, PHE581, ALA610, ASP580, LEU553, ASN531, ASN530, and ASN554. **Figure 7** displays the interacting residues discovered by docking and compares the interactions between ligand-protein residues in the mutant (N44H, S207C, D84A, N185S) and native TLR4 proteins, highlighting how the mutations alter the functional properties.

Figure 7. Interaction of protein ligands with *TLR4* with Apigenin (a), S-adenosylmethionine (b), Tetracycline (c), Tetrodotoxin(d) and (e)Vixotrigine.

The ligands interact with *TLR4* protein and play a critical role in modulating its function. *TLR4* is involved in the innate immune response and recognizes PAMPs and DAMPs, triggering inflammation and immune activation. 1. Apigenin is known for its anti-inflammatory properties. By binding to *TLR4*, Apigenin may inhibit the receptor's activation, reducing the inflammatory response. Its interactions with residues like TYR403, GLU376, and ARG355 in the binding pocket can potentially interfere with the downstream signaling pathways, which could help in controlling inflammation. As an antibiotic, Tetracycline can modulate immune responses by interacting with *TLR4*. It may reduce *TLR4*-mediated signaling by binding to the receptor and

disrupting its function. This could be useful in mitigating excessive immune activation, which is often observed in chronic inflammation and autoimmune diseases. Tetrodotoxin is a potent neurotoxin that blocks sodium channels. Its binding to *TLR4* may modulate immune responses by influencing *TLR4* signaling, potentially altering the activation of inflammatory pathways. The exact effect of Tetrodotoxin on *TLR4* signaling is not fully understood but may involve the inhibition of *TLR4*-mediated immune responses. S-adenosylmethionine (SAM) is a key molecule involved in methylation reactions and has anti-inflammatory properties. It may modulate *TLR4* activity by regulating its signaling pathways, possibly through epigenetic modifications. Its

interaction with residues like ALA610, ASN554, and PHE581 may affect the receptor's ability to respond to inflammatory stimuli, thereby reducing the immune response. Vixotrigine, a sodium channel blocker, may have an effect on *TLR4*-mediated signaling, particularly in inflammatory diseases. Its binding with residues such as MET607, PHE581, and ALA610 could impact the receptor's conformation and reduce the activation of inflammatory pathways, making it a potential therapeutic agent for conditions involving *TLR4*-driven inflammation. In summary, these ligands can interact with *TLR4*, potentially altering its structure and function. By either inhibiting or modulating the *TLR4* signaling pathway, they may serve as therapeutic agents for diseases driven by excessive or chronic inflammation. The effectiveness of these compounds is further supported by their strong binding affinities and specific interactions with key residues of the *TLR4* receptor.

DISCUSSION

Conjunctivitis is a common ophthalmic disease that causes inflammation of the conjunctival tissues. Clinical symptoms include increased discharge, conjunctival congestion, photophobia, and itchy sensations [36]. The nsSNPs are single base variations that alter the encoded protein's amino acid sequence. Studies have examined how nsSNPs affect specific proteins, such as stability and the active sites of enzymes. These investigations 53 examine the different ways that nsSNPs may impact interactions between proteins. Before examining the investigation of nsSNPs from a network viewpoint, we focus on structural alterations that might hinder interaction, changes to disorder, gain of interaction, and post-translational modifications. Here are some instances of nsSNPs at human-pathogen protein-protein interfaces [37]. Toll-like receptor 4 (TLR4), expressed in various cells, forms the foundation of the mammalian innate immune

system, which is characterized by malfunctioning in different situations [38]. TLR4 SNP is linked to various diseases and dysfunctions in patient populations. TLR4 targeting may not be a cure, impacting drug use and polypharmacy. Its flexibility in binding to various ligands contributes to its flexibility [38]. The study identified 132 missense mutations common in SIFT and Polyhen databases, 82 nsSNPs using 10 repository tools, and analyzed high RMSD mutants using TM align for structural effects. We use computational tools to analyze molecular docking studies to predict protein-ligand interaction and analyze diseases causing SNPs and their impact on protein stability. The study utilized various prediction tools to analyze pathogenic nsSNPs of the TLR4 gene, revealing that 96 out of 132 nsSNPs may be harmful, with 28 SNP variants likely to be benign. The predicted SNPs revealed that 104 out of 132 nsSNPs had a negative effect, 28 were neutral, and all 128 SNPs were likely to be damaging. Apart from the possibly damaged Y652C, the benign S415T, I769T, and P168H are also present. SNP &G0 prediction shows that 14 of the 118 substitutions are neutral and linked to illness. The Meta SNP database identified 42 neutral nsSNPs and 90 disease nsSNPs. SuSpect found 132 nsSNPs associated with the disease. Functional analysis revealed that the TLR4 gene has detrimental, potentially damaging effects and a disease effect. These 132 nsSNPs were used to predict the effect of the gene on protein stability. The 132 disease-associated nsSNPs were put in the I-stable to evaluate their effect on protein stability. Since I-stable predicts changes in protein thermal stability, 24 nsSNPs indicated increasing stability and 111 nsSNPs showed decreasing protein thermal stability. Out of 82 nsSNPs in SAVES, 82 mutations were analyzed, but 22 results were shown by 3D mutation. Utilizing a mutation 3D tool, we analyze the functional impact of genetic mutations on disease mechanisms, gene function,

and personalized medicine, predicting potential protein function impacts. Out of 82 mutations, we find 1 uncovered mutation, 13 clustered mutations, and 10 covered mutations based on mutation 3D. A more thorough analysis of the 132 nsSNPs is conducted for structural validation. The experimental model for a higher-quality targeted protein structure was validated using various computational programs like TM-Align, verify 3D, SWISS-MODEL, PROCHECK, QMEAN, and ERRAT. The server produced 132 templates, 1 of which was Q9TTN0.1.A., based on the best-aligned template. Our targeted protein's whole sequence was covered by a toll-like receptor. The model, interestingly, fell within the amino acid range of 839, which may be 56 suggesting that the protein sequence surrounding this region is conserved. The Ramachandran plot is a crucial verification matrix as it displays the ϕ - ψ torsion angles of the predicted protein backbone. PROCHECK divides the Ramachandran plot into four regions: core, allowed, generously allowed, and disallowed. This allows it to estimate the stereochemical quality of a particular protein structure. The Ramachandran plot's preferred region is described by SWISS-MODEL. Over 90% of core or most favored residues in protein models can be identified with a favorable structure, with scores provided by other computational tools. A QMEAN-Z score of -4.0 or less denotes a low-quality model, while a higher score identifies favorable structural states. Using the TM-align tool, a structural comparison between the wild-type and mutant structures was examined. A high RMSD value and a low TM score both point to structural dissimilarity. The Swiss model indicates that the generated structure is of good quality and suitable for protein-ligand studies. For additional examination, one model and four mutated proteins were chosen based on the validation software's standard score. The PyRx Autodock vina 0.4 software was used to perform

docking for 16 drugs and their 5 potential targets. It provided a docking score along with energy minimization values. Out of 16 ligands and 5 protein interactions, the molecular docking studies have revealed that the drug-target interactions of the Model-Apigenin complex were -6.5, the Model-Tetracycline complex was -7.0, the Model-Tetrodotoxin complex was -6.4, the Model-S-adenosylmethionine complex was -6.3, and the Model-Vixotrigine complex was -7.1. These results represent the highest docking scores with energy minimization. The interaction between the ligand and target complex was observed using Discovery Studio Visualizer. A protein's evolutionary conservation profile can be used to gauge how severe a harmful mutation is. Further research is necessary to understand pathogenicity, protein stability, and disease-related nsSNPs. Computational tools will be used in conjunction with wet and dry lab docking analyses of nsSNPs in *TLR4* to find novel medications for the treatment of conjunctivitis. When interpreting genetic test results and deciding on a course of treatment, medical professionals can gain from the clinical application of in silico analysis. Experimental research on the functional impact of nsSNPs on immune function is informed by in silico predictions because *TLR4* is an essential part of the human immune system. Information about therapeutic targets and the pathophysiology of disease is provided by this method. Computation biologists, physicians, and pharmaceutical companies must collaborate to translate in silico discoveries into clinical applications. Improving patient outcomes and quality of life for people with diseases related to *TLR4* is the goal.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, through the use of various computational tools, we conducted an in-depth analysis of *TLR4* gene SNPs, categorizing them based on their pathogenicity. We found 132 were

classified as highly pathogenic and deleterious from 82 missense variants, while the remaining SNPs were considered likely neutral. Structural analysis revealed that these pathogenic variants cause significant disruption to the protein structure and stability, suggesting that they alter the protein function by affecting the normal 3D conformation of the *TLR4* protein. Although rs897794510 exhibited similar results for mutant and wild-type sizes, HOPE modeling for variants such as rs199930089, rs1235644534, rs1282672274, rs746352626, and rs760962514 suggested that the mutant size was larger than the wild type. Variants like rs199930089, rs1282672274, and rs746352626 were identified as pathogenic and potentially harmful, while others such as rs368003192 and rs1314441656 were also considered likely harmful. Molecular docking simulations were performed using Pyrx, where the modeled structure of the TLR4 protein was docked with 16 different ligands to predict binding site conformations and ligand orientations. The compounds Vixotrigine, Tetracycline, Apigenin, Tetrodotoxin, and S-adenosylmethionine showed promising binding energy levels. Based on these findings, future research into diseases associated with conjunctivitis should focus on these nsSNPs as primary targets. Since this is the first in-silico study analyzing *TLR4* gene variants, it provides a foundation for future experimental studies on diseases related to these polymorphisms. Furthermore, mutational studies could offer deeper insights into the specific functional consequences of these SNPs.

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Declaration of Conflict

No Conflict of Interest.

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